

Rebound effect explains the divergence in survival after 5 days in a controlled trial on vitamin C for COVID-19 patients

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This supplement contains the figures that were analyzed in the paper.

Figure 2C of Adhikari et al. [17] was extracted from the paper and used in our analyses.

17. LOVIT-COVID Investigators, on behalf of the Canadian Critical Care Trials Group, and the REMAP-CAP Investigators; Adhikari NKJ et al. Intravenous vitamin C for patients hospitalized with COVID-19: two harmonized randomized clinical trials. JAMA. 2023;330(18):1745-1759. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2023.21407> <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10600726>

Adhikari et al. published the survival curves for vitamin C and control groups over 90 days. We show the period up to 15 days, since the termination of vitamin C administration took place after 4 days and therefore this range is most relevant when considering potential effects of vitamin C and its abrupt termination. While there is evidence that the survival curves differ between days 5 to 7.5, there is no evidence that the survival curves differ between days 15 and 90 days with 95%CI for the RR: 0.73 to 1.18, see page 7. Thus, publishing the Figure 2C with the time range up to 90 days [17] camouflages the divergence at the early part of the curves and thereby misleads the readers.

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In **Figure A** (extracted from [17]) we drew blue guide lines to show the divergence between the two groups. Using a graphics program, we measured the positions as pixels from the upper left corner and transformed the measurements to the units of the axis. Our Figures A to C can be extracted from this PDF file. We determined that the survival curves started to diverge at 5.0 days and the blue lines crossed at a cumulative proportion of mortality of 0.094, which corresponds to 98 deaths in the vitamin C group and 50 deaths in the control group. See the calculation below the Figure.

No. at risk	
Vitamin C	1037 763
Control	531 414

Horizontal (days)			Start of divergence
	Pixels	Pixel difference	Days
15	1764	754	15.00
blue	1261	251	4.99
0.0	1010		

Vertical (cumulative mortality)			Mortality at divergence
	Pixels	Pixel difference	
0.3	410	1642	0.3000
blue	1537	515	0.0941
0.0	2052		

	Vitamin C	Control
Time 0	1037	531
At 4.8 days	97.6	50.0
Rounded to	98	50
At risk at day 5	939	481
Alive at day 15	763	414
Died between day 5 and day 15	176	67
Rate of death between day 5 and 15	0.19	0.14
RR for death between days 5 and 15	1.346	

Slopes	Pixels	Pixel difference	RR
Vitamin C	159	1378	2.51
Control	987	550	
0.0	1537		

The pixel levels are measured at day 15

The "0-level" indicates the level at the blue horizontal line (mortality level 0.0941)

In **Figure B** (extracted from [17]) we drew parallel blue guide lines to show that the survival curves of the two groups are parallel after the short-term divergence. The vertical line indicates the approximate start of the parallel region.

We determined that the parallelism starts at about 10 days, see calculation below the Figure.

Figure 2C_B: Estimation of the start of the parallelism

Horizontal (Days)	Start of parallelism		Days
	Pixels	Pixel difference	
15	1764	754	15.0
blue	1518	508	10.1
0.0	1010		

In **Figure C** (extracted from [17]) we drew a blue guide line to estimate the levels of the survival curves when the divergence started to level off. The blue line is located at 7.5 days, see calculation of the survival curve levels below the Figure.

No. at risk	
Vitamin C	1037
Control	531

	Vitamin C	Control
Time 0	1037	531
	0.1490	0.1185
At 7.5 days	154.5	62.9
Rounded to	154	63
At risk at day 5	939	481
Died between day 5 and day 7.5	56	13
Alive at day 7.5	883	468
Rate of death between day 5 and 7.5	0.060	0.027
RR for death between days 5 and 7.5	2.207	

Calculation of the RR to compare vitamin C and control groups

Time range 5 to 15 days (compare page 2)

Printout of the R program

```
riskratio.wald(COVIDd15)
```

```
$data
```

Predictor	Outcome		
	Disease1	Disease2	Total
Exposed1	414	67	481
Exposed2	763	176	939
Total	1177	243	1420

```
$measure
```

Predictor	risk ratio with 95% C.I.		
	estimate	lower	upper
Exposed1	1.00	NA	NA
Exposed2	1.35	1.04	1.74

```
$p.value
```

Predictor	two-sided		
	midp.exact	fisher.exact	chi.square
Exposed1	NA	NA	NA
Exposed2	0.0215	0.0254	0.0226

```
$correction
```

```
[1] FALSE
```

```
attr(,"method")
```

```
[1] "Unconditional MLE & normal approximation (Wald) CI"
```

Time range 5 to 7.5 days (compare page 4)
Printout of the R program

```
riskratio.wald(COVIDd7.5)
$data
      Outcome
Predictor Disease1 Disease2 Total
  Exposed1     468      13    481
  Exposed2     883      56    939
  Total       1351      69   1420

$measure
      risk ratio with 95% C.I.
Predictor estimate lower upper
  Exposed2     2.21  1.22  3.99

$p.value
      two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact chi.square
  Exposed1          NA          NA          NA
  Exposed2    0.00525    0.00602    0.00683

$correction
[1] FALSE

attr(,"method")
[1] "Unconditional MLE & normal approximation (Wald) CI"
```

Time range 15 to 90 days of Figure 2C [17]
Printout of the R program

```
> #Deads after 15 days
> #Control
> (414-329)
[1] 85
> #vit C
> (763-617)
[1] 146
>
> COVIDd90<- matrix(c(329,617, 85,146),nrow=2)
> riskratio.wald(COVIDd90)
$data
      Outcome
Predictor Disease1 Disease2 Total
  Exposed1      329       85   414
  Exposed2      617      146   763
  Total         946      231  1177

$measure
      risk ratio with 95% C.I.
Predictor estimate lower upper
  Exposed1      1.000      NA      NA
  Exposed2      0.932  0.734  1.18

$p.value
      two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact chi.square
  Exposed1          NA          NA          NA
  Exposed2      0.564      0.591      0.565
```

Improvement in Poisson regression by adding vitamin C effect on day range 5.0 to 7.5 days.

Fig. A indicates that the divergence between the vitamin C and control curves starts at about 5.0 days. Fig. C indicates that the divergence between the vitamin C and control curves ends at about 7.5 days.

Here we calculate the improvement in the Poisson regression model when an independent vitamin C effect is allowed for the time range 5.0 to 7.5 days.

period1 indicates time before 5.0 days, with N=531 (control) and N=1037 (vitC), see Fig. C.

period2 indicates time range 5.0 to 7.5 days, with N=481 (control) and N= 939 (vitC), see Fig. C.

period3 indicates time range 7.5 to 90 days, with N=468 (control) and N= 883 (vitC), see Fig. C.

pdays is the product of persons at the baseline and the days of followup.

For example, on period 2, the pdays is $481 \times 2.5 \text{ days} = 1202.5 \text{ pdays}$ in the control group (vitC=0).

deaths during the three time periods were estimated in Figs. A and C.

```
> Adhikari2023
  vitC period2 period3 deaths days persons  pdays
1     0         0         0     50  5.0     531 2655.0
2     0         1         0     13  2.5     481 1202.5
3     0         0         1    139 82.5     468 38610.0
4     1         0         0     98  5.0    1037 5185.0
5     1         1         0     56  2.5     939 2347.5
6     1         0         1    266 82.5     883 72847.5
```

1. The Poisson model that assumes a uniform vitamin C effect over the 90 days.

```
> summary(covid1)
```

Call:

```
glm(formula = deaths ~ offset(log(pdays)) + vitC + period2 +
    period3, family = poisson(), data = Adhikari2023)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-4.02693	0.10074	-39.973	<2e-16	***
vitC	0.08519	0.08563	0.995	0.320	
period2	0.02919	0.14577	0.200	0.841	
period3	-1.64708	0.09605	-17.147	<2e-16	***

AIC: 51.365

2. The model that allows an independent vitamin C effect for the time period 5.0 to 7.5 days.

Here we test whether the vitamin C effect is different in period2:
we add the interaction term between period2 and the vitamin C effect.

```
> summary(covid2)
```

Call:

```
glm(formula = deaths ~ offset(log(pdays)) + vitC * period2 +  
    period3, family = poisson(), data = Adhikari2023)
```

Deviance Residuals:

1	2	3	4	5	6
0.03627	0.00000	-0.02170	-0.02584	0.00000	0.01570

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-3.97731	0.10149	-39.190	<2e-16	***
vitC	0.01136	0.08966	0.127	0.8992	
period2	-0.54990	0.29534	-1.862	0.0626	.
period3	-1.64764	0.09605	-17.153	<2e-16	***
vitC:period2	0.78009	0.32065	2.433	0.0150	*

AIC: 46.658

Addition of the different vitamin C effect to the second period improves the statistical model by $\chi^2 = 6.7$ which corresponds to **P = 0.0096**.

```
lrtest(covid1,covid2)  
Likelihood ratio test
```

```
Model 1: deaths ~ offset(log(pdays)) + vitC + period2 + period3  
Model 2: deaths ~ offset(log(pdays)) + vitC * period2 + period3  
#Df  LogLik Df  Chisq Pr(>Chisq)  
1    4 -21.682  
2    5 -18.329  1  6.7069  0.009604 **
```

As expected, the vitamin C effect in period2 is very close to the RR = 2.21 calculated on page 6:

```
> exp(0.78009)  
[1] 2.181669
```

3. The model that allows a different vitamin C effect for each of the three time periods.

Finally, we test whether the vitamin C effect is different between periods 1 and 3: we further add the interaction term between period3 and the vitamin C effect.

```
> summary(covid3)
```

Call:

```
glm(formula = deaths ~ offset(log(pdays)) + vitC * period2 +  
    vitC * period3, family = poisson(), data = Adhikari2023)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)	-3.972177	0.141421	-28.088	<2e-16	***
vitC	0.003619	0.173793	0.021	0.9834	
period2	-0.555032	0.311325	-1.783	0.0746	.
period3	-1.654616	0.164907	-10.034	<2e-16	***
vitC:period2	0.787835	0.353531	2.228	0.0258	*
vitC:period3	0.010546	0.202874	0.052	0.9585	

AIC: 48.655

Addition of the different vitamin C effect to the third time period does not improve the statistical model at all. Change in χ^2 corresponds to P = 0.96.

```
> lrtest(covid2, covid3)
```

Likelihood ratio test

Model 1: deaths ~ offset(log(pdays)) + vitC * period2 + period3

Model 2: deaths ~ offset(log(pdays)) + vitC * period2 + vitC * period3

	#Df	LogLik	Df	Chisq	Pr(>Chisq)
1	5	-18.329			
2	6	-18.328	1	0.0027	0.9586

Allowing separate vitamin C effects for each of the three periods makes the period2 vitamin C effect even closer to the RR = 2.21 calculated on page 6.

```
> exp(0.78783)
```

```
[1] 2.199
```